

ANALYSIS OF UNSTEADY PRESSURE LOADS ON THE THEMIS T3 VEHICLE IN UNPROPELLED BACKWARD FLIGHT

Tim Horchler and Mariasole Laureti

German Aerospace Center (DLR)
Institute of Aerodynamics and Flow Technology, Spacecraft Department.
Bunsenstrasse 10, 37073 Göttingen, Germany

ABSTRACT

The commercial success of the SpaceX Falcon 9 rocket has proven that reusable space launch systems are viable concepts for increasing the efficiency and reducing the cost to access space. Even though this system has been operational since 2015, no other company from the sector of space transportation has yet managed to successfully land the first stage of a rocket, neither in Europe, Asia or the US. In order to facilitate the development of a reusable launcher in Europe, the EU has financed several programs and initiatives to develop Vertical Take-off Vertical Landing (VTVL) capabilities. One of these is the Horizon Europe project SALTO (reusable Strategic Launcher Technologies and Operations) with support from ESAs Themis program. The goal is to design a rocket prototype to deliver up to 2000 kg into low Earth orbit. Themis uses the Prometheus Methane-LOx engine and is designed for reusability with a landing accuracy of 20 x 20 meters. During the project SALTO, several hop tests are anticipated. This current study focuses on the aspect of unsteady pressure loads on different parts of a reference configuration for a future demonstrator, also known as the T3 vehicle. In this work we will use the DLR TAU code together with a scale-resolving detached-eddy simulation (DES) turbulence model to resolve vortex shedding and the impingement of vortices on different parts of the vehicle at two flight conditions. The results show the spatial distribution and amplitude of pressure fluctuations on the vehicle surface and help to identify the regions of highest loads. By using methods from signal analysis, the study also provides frequency spectra of the unsteady pressure loads that could serve as an input for structural analysis. This paper will also investigate the sensitivity of predicted unsteady pressure loads towards mesh refinement.

Index Terms— reusability, numerical simulation, unsteady pressure loads, CFD

1. INTRODUCTION

While aerothermal load predictions are of primary concern for VTVL launcher concepts in almost all phases of flight,

unsteady pressure loads on small surface structures have received much less attention in the past. This was mainly due to the high numerical cost associated with these types of studies as one needs time-accurate simulations to resolve the fluctuating time scales. With the increasing availability of high-performance computing (HPC) resources, such studies become more and more feasible and will be an essential part in the vehicle design phase. This work uses time-resolved improved delayed detached-eddy simulations (iDDES) to investigate unsteady pressure loads on the vehicle surface for two different flight Mach numbers (one sub- and one supersonic) at 5-degree angle of attack. All simulations use the T3 vehicle geometry and investigate the unpowered gliding phase back to the landing location.

Fig. 1. Base region overview of the T3 reference configuration for a future demonstrator.

The primary goal of this paper is to provide unsteady pressure loads at single-point locations on the nozzle extensions. On a more global perspective, this paper will provide the integrated and normalized RMS pressure load on the overall vehicle surface for a faster identification of the relevant areas with high fluctuating activity. We will give a detailed overview of the simulation modelling and post-processing strategy used in the first part of this paper. The second part will show the simulation results and the analysis for the sub- and supersonic flow case. In the last part, the simulation results will be discussed and conclusions will be drawn.

2. NUMERICAL SETUP

All results in this paper are produced using the DLR TAU code [1]. TAU is a second-order compressible finite-volume solver for flow simulations on hybrid, fully unstructured and structured meshes. Using its edge-based dual-cell approach based on the vertex-centres, it has been applied to a large variety of flows ranging from the low subsonic regime to chemically reacting hypersonic re-entry flows. The time-accurate simulations in this work use a Jameson-type dual time stepping approach with a physical time step size of 2×10^{-6} s. The inner iterations in the dual time stepping approach are advanced using a fully implicit Backward Euler scheme with a CFL number of 20. Typically, each physical time step converges within 30-40 inner iterations once the monitoring variables (lift coefficient c_l , drag coefficient c_d , total vorticity ω , total turbulent kinetic energy k and maximum eddy viscosity μ_T) are converged to a relative value of 5×10^{-6} . TAU uses a second-order spatial discretization with a least-square based gradient reconstruction. The numerical fluxes are calculated using a modified central discretization scheme with improved dissipation and dispersion (low-dissipation low-dispersion, labelled LD2) properties [2]. TAU has been validated using different detached-eddy scale-resolving turbulence model schemes. This work uses the improved Delayed Detached-Eddy simulation (iDDES) approach of Shur et al. [3]. In a similar setup, TAU has also been extensively used to analyse the wake flow of a generic forward-flying rocket configuration [4]. The hybrid mesh used for our investigations here has been created using CENTAUR and contains approximately 16 mio grid points for both Mach number cases. In order to investigate the influence of the grid resolution on the unsteady pressure loads, a finer mesh consisting of 36.7 mio points has been used for the subsonic case. The overall meshing strategy and the regions of highest refinement are shown in Fig. 2.

(a) Base region overview (b) Zoom into refined nozzle mesh.

Fig. 2. Images of the refined mesh regions around the launcher base

An overview of the trajectory points considered in this work is given in Tbl. 1.

Table 1. Overview of the simulated trajectory points.

Property	Unit	subsonic baseline	subsonic fine	supersonic
Sim. time	s	0.995	1.047	1.118
Mach number	-	0.9	0.9	1.5
AoA	deg	5	5	5
Wall temp	K	300	300	300
No. grid points	mio	16.55	36.72	16.62

2.1. Data evaluation strategy

All unsteady iDDES were run for approximately one full second of physical time. At the given physical simulation time step size of 2×10^{-6} s, we output surface solution files at every 100 timesteps resulting in a sampling frequency of $f_s = 5$ kHz. Based on the total simulation time, the frequency resolution is therefore approximately $\Delta f = 1$ Hz. From the time resolved surface solution files, two paths for data analysis are followed:

1. For the determination of the surface root-mean-square (RMS) pressure distribution, the RMS values are calculated for all surface points by

$$\frac{p_{\text{RMS}}}{p_{\text{dyn}}} = \frac{\sqrt{\langle (p - \langle p \rangle)^2 \rangle}}{\frac{1}{2} \rho_{\infty} u_{\infty}^2} \quad (1)$$

which also includes a normalization with the dynamic pressure. These results will be later presented as surface contours.

2. For the single-point surface data analysis, the pressure time signal at the pre-defined measurement points is first filtered by a third-order Butterworth low-pass filter at the cut-off frequency of $f_c = 2$ kHz. Then, the filtered time signal is converted into a power spectral density spectrum by using a sample-length of 1024. The data is then presented in terms of the non-dimensional Strouhal number Sr and a non-dimensionalized power spectral density:

$$Sr = \frac{f \cdot L_{\text{ref}}}{u_{\infty}} \quad (2)$$

$$\text{PSD}' = \text{PSD}(f) \cdot \frac{u_{\infty}}{q_{\infty}^2 \cdot L_{\text{ref}}} \quad (3)$$

For the calculation of the turbulent time scale $T_{\text{turb.}}$, we use a normalized auto-correlation function of the fluctuating pressure signal $p' = p - \langle p \rangle$:

$$C(\tau) = C(k \cdot \Delta T) = \frac{\sum_n p'_{n+k} \cdot p'_n}{\sum_n p_n'^2} \quad (4)$$

Here, we define $T_{\text{turb.}} = \tau$ for the first zero-crossing where $C(\tau) = 0$.

3. RESULTS

3.1. Qualitative Overview of the Turbulent Flow Field around the Launcher Base

For the visualization of turbulent flow field, the Q -criterion is commonly used to display vortical structures in computational fluid dynamics. For better comparability, the value of Q is also non-dimensionalized by the reference velocity and a typical length scale (e.g. the launcher diameter D):

$$Q = Q' \cdot \frac{u_\infty^2}{D^2} \quad (5)$$

Then, a suitable value for the non-dimensional Q' is chosen. In this work, a value of 50 is used. The visualization in Fig. 3 shows the main region of vortex shedding from the nozzle extensions and the base plate. As the incoming air hits the sharp corners at the nozzle extension and the base plate, vortices are shed downstream of the vehicle base. Due to the 5-degree angle of attack, a large recirculation zone is formed on the leeward side of the vehicle. As the angle of attack is not high enough, vorticity leaving the outer nozzle extensions will impinge on the rim of the base plate. It will be confirmed later by the surface RMS pressure plots that this is indeed the region of highest-pressure fluctuation on the vehicle.

Fig. 3. Visualization of the vortical structures around the T3 vehicle using the Q -criterion. A non-dimensional value of $Q' = 50$ was chosen.

In contrast to the $Ma = 0.9$ case, there are less vortical structures visible for the $Ma = 1.5$ case. This is caused by the higher (dimensional) value of Q for the visualization while the (non-dimensional) Q' is the same as for the low speed case. With the freestream in flow velocity being significantly higher for the $Ma = 1.5$ case, the vortices still have a very similar strength because the post-shock velocity for the $Ma = 1.5$ is almost identical to the freestream velocity of the $Ma = 0.9$ case. If one normalizes the Q value with the post-shock speed for the $Ma = 1.5$ case, a similar picture emerges, see Fig. 4. Due to the different flow topologies caused by the detached bow shock, the structure of the recirculation zone is different for the high-speed case.

Fig. 4. Isosurfaces of $Q' = 50$ but normalized with the post-shock velocity.

3.2. Normalized Surface RMS Pressure for Mach = 0.9 Case

This section presents the spatial distribution of the integral surface RMS pressure fluctuations on the launch vehicle. While the results shown here are not resolved in frequency space, this representation gives a good overview of the regions of highest activity. A more detailed, point-based analysis in frequency space will be given later.

Fig. 5. Normalized surface RMS pressure distribution for the $Ma = 0.9$ case.

Fig. 5 shows the surface RMS pressure distribution on the nozzle extensions and the launcher body. The colour scale represents the percentage of the RMS pressure value with respect to the dynamic free stream pressure. The maximum value of RMS pressure fluctuation is obtained on the outer surface of the nozzle extension with 42.2 %. On the

launcher body, the values are generally lower with up to 20 % of the freestream dynamic pressure. The surface RMS pictures highlight the main recirculation region which extends to approximately half the height of the landing leg covers. A slightly higher activity is also seen on the leeward side, as expected, while there are strong pressure oscillations on both sides of the nozzle extensions (lee- and windward side).

The region of second highest pressure fluctuations is the base plate with up to 41.4 % of the freestream dynamic pressure, as shown in Fig. 6.

Fig. 6. Zoom on the normalized surface RMS pressure distribution on the baseplate and the nozzle extensions for the $Ma = 0.9$ case.

Most of the base plate’s activity is located on the leeward edge of the rocket body where the vortices impinge that originated from the flow around the nozzle. Their footprint has been already highlighted in Fig. 3 where one can clearly see how the vortices are formed around the nozzle extensions and are then being convected downstream towards the face plate. The position of this region is, of course, sensitive to the angle of attack and is likely to disappear when the angle is increased further.

A more detailed view on the surface pressure distribution on the nozzle extensions is given in Fig. 6 (bottom). One notices the large gradients and strong variation in the surface RMS pressure distribution on the nozzles. Compared to all other parts of the vehicle surface, the outer nozzle walls show the highest spatial gradients in the pressure fluctuations. This high variability has implications for the further analysis of

the single-point pressure data and the comparison with results from other sources: Choosing slightly different analysis points or having mesh points at different locations may result in vastly different results. This again strengthens the usefulness of the spatially resolved RMS pressure plots because they allow for a global comparison in contrast to the single-point analysis that will be given later.

The surface RMS pressure distribution has been further decomposed into modes by Proper Orthogonal Decomposition [5] (POD). However, this decomposition did not result in any further insight into the mode structure and did not reveal any dominant eigenmodes. Therefore, no results of the POD analysis are shown in this paper.

3.3. Normalized Surface RMS Pressure for Mach = 1.5 Case

For a better comparison of the sub- and supersonic cases, the following pictures for the $Ma = 1.5$ supersonic case are shown in the same colour scale as the previous results. While the overall structure of the unsteady pressure load is very similar to the $Ma = 0.9$ case, the results of the supersonic simulation show generally lower relative RMS pressure values.

Fig. 7. Normalized surface RMS pressure distribution for the $Ma = 1.5$ case.

The highest activity is again predicted on the outer side of the nozzle extensions, as well as the launcher base plate. A more detailed view of the baseplate is given in Fig. 8

The detailed view on the nozzle extension outer surface of Fig. 8 shows again the curved nozzle like shape of the region of highest activity. Though lower in amplitude, its shape is very similar to the $Ma = 0.9$ case.

Fig. 8. Zoom on the normalized surface RMS pressure distribution on the baseplate and the nozzle extensions for the $Ma = 1.5$ case.

A summary of the maximum RMS pressure values (as percentage of the freestream dynamic pressure) is given in Tbl. 2. The maximum surface RMS amplitude for the supersonic case is approximately 10 % lower than for the subsonic case while the values encountered on the body remain essentially the same.

Table 2. Summary of maximum surface RMS values for the sub- and supersonic configuration

Part	Maximum RMS	
	$Ma = 0.9$	$Ma = 1.5$
Baseplate	41.1 %	32.4 %
Nozzle	42.2 %	32.0 %
Body	20.0 %	18.9 %

3.4. Single-Point Spectra

In this section, the single-point pressure spectra will be presented and analyzed. Virtual sensors are placed in rings of equal axial location on the outside and inside of the nozzle extensions. For the analysis of the single-point spectra, the sensor points are not directly located on the nozzle lip but moved upstream 15 % of the nozzle diameter, i.e. towards the nozzle throat. The reason for this is to capture partially

the recirculation zone behind the nozzle and to allow for the formation of vortices.

Single-point power spectral density plots are shown for two locations on two different nozzles. The outer nozzle (based on its orientation in the local coordinate system also denoted as the $y+$ -nozzle) is the main source of vortex production in the base region. This is already highlighted by the Q -isosurface plots in Fig. 3 and the baseplate footprint of the pressure oscillations shown in Fig. 6. To give some more insight into the resolved pressure spectra, Fig. 9 compares the power spectral density at the leeward side (90° position) of the $y+$ nozzle for the $Ma = 0.9$ and $Ma = 1.5$ simulations.

Fig. 9. Comparison on the non-dimensionalized power spectral density at the outer nozzle.

The top PSD plot in Fig. 9 shows the pressure spectral density on the nozzle outside, the bottom one on the nozzle inside. It should be noted that the pressure fluctuations inside the nozzle are about two orders of magnitude smaller than on the nozzle outside. The nozzle outside spectrum is dominated by a low-frequency peak below a Strouhal number of 0.2. A similar peak is also seen for the nozzle inside but only for the supersonic case $Ma = 1.5$. Apart from this low-frequency contribution, no clear secondary peak is visible on the nozzle outside.

The power spectral density at the central nozzle Fig. 10 is generally lower on the nozzle outside (compared to the $y+$ -nozzle) and does not show a significant low-frequency contribution. Here, however, we see a weak distinct peak around $Sr = 0.2$ and more pronounced peak at $Sr = 0.8$ for the $Ma = 1.5$ simulation. Also, the supersonic trajectory point shows a higher unsteady pressure load even after non-dimensionalization. At the central nozzle, the $Ma = 1.5$ simulations shows large low-frequency contribution on the nozzle inside compared to the subsonic simulation at $Ma = 0.9$

Due to their presentation in frequency (or Strouhal number) space, the single-point spectra require more samples until convergence is achieved compared to the RMS pressure representations shown before. However, these samples must

Fig. 10. Comparison on the non-dimensionalized power spectral density at the central nozzle.

be statistically independent, otherwise the problem could be solved by simply oversampling.

How can two time-resolved pressure signals be tested if they are statistically independent? For turbulent flows, this is usually done by calculating the auto-correlation function Eq. 4 of the signals and determining the time of the first zero-crossing. This correlation time, also known as the turbulent time scale $T_{\text{turb.}}$, is computed as a post-processing step for all surface points of the T3 numerical model. The statistical distribution of the turbulent time-scale for the sub- and supersonic trajectory point is given in Fig. 11.

Fig. 11. Statistical distribution of the surface turbulent pressure timescale for all surface points.

We find rather broad distributions of the turbulent time scale ranging from 0.75 ms - 3 ms. To make the two cases comparable, a Rayleigh distribution is fitted to the histograms and the mean values are calculated. For the supersonic trajectory point ($Ma = 1.5$), $T_{\text{turb.}}$ is estimated to be 2.00 milliseconds while for the subsonic flow, the turbulent time scale is larger with 2.41 ms. This means that only 400 - 500 usable samples are available for one second of simulation time. Such a sample size might be enough for the integrated surface pressure RMS distribution but if these time series are further decomposed in frequency space, the sample size seems to be insufficient to provide converged spectra.

3.5. Analysis of the Mesh Resolution for Scale-Resolving Simulations

In contrast to steady RANS simulations, it is usually infeasible to assess the required grid resolution of scale-resolving, e.g. LES or hybrid-DES methods, by systematically varying the grid resolution and compare simulation results. One reason for this is the associated high computational cost of unsteady and finely resolved simulations. Grid convergence can't also be guaranteed as the amount of directly resolved turbulent structures depends on the LES filter width. On the other hand, the finer the grid is chosen, the smaller are the scales that can actually be resolved. From a conceptual point of view, the idea of grid convergence studies can therefore not be transferred directly to Large-Eddy and Detached-Eddy simulations.

For scale-resolving simulations it is more useful [6] to compare the ratio of resolved turbulent kinetic energy k_{res} to the total turbulent kinetic energy, i.e. the sum of resolved and modelled (subgrid-scale or SGS) turbulent kinetic energy:

$$S_1 = \frac{k_{\text{res}}}{k_{\text{res}} + k_{\text{SGS}}} \quad (6)$$

This value S_1 is denoted as the grid sensor and represents a measure how well the grid can resolve turbulent structures. Literature suggests that 80 % of the turbulent kinetic energy should be explicitly resolved for a proper scale-resolving simulation.

Fig. 12. Visualization of the mesh sensor S_1 for the $Ma = 1.5$ case

The value of the grid sensor is shown in two different cut planes for the $Ma = 1.5$ case in Fig. 12. The chosen cut-off value for a sufficiently resolved Detached-Eddy simulation (DES) is given by the white contour line. In both images, one notices the deliberately refined mesh regions around the vehicle base that allow for a proper development of resolved turbulent structures. In these regions, more than 90 % of the turbulent kinetic energy is resolved and it can be concluded that the mesh is generally fine enough. Both images, however, show that the region around the detached shock is strongly under resolved even though the mesh size doesn't change there significantly compared to the near-nozzle region. We believe

that this is caused by the interaction of the grid sensor with the bow-shock. The grid sensor implementation was originally designed only for subsonic flow velocities and it might therefore give misleading results in region with large flow gradients, e.g. shocks.

Due to the 5° angle of attack, one notices differences between the windward and the leeward side of the T3 vehicle in Fig. 12. While the top side is generally well resolved beyond 90 %, the bottom side is clearly under resolved even though the cell sizes are the same on both sides. The reason for this is the lack of vortex shedding on the windward side. Therefore, the ratio of resolved-to-total-turbulence is higher on the top side where a large number of vortices are shed from the nozzle lip and base ring. This difference is also seen in the Q -isosurface image of the $Ma = 1.5$ trajectory point in Fig. 3.

Fig. 13. Vortical structures at $Q' = 50$ colored with the value of the grid sensor.

Another interesting feature of Detached-Eddy simulations can be noticed if one uses the grid sensor to colour the isosurfaces of the vortical structures shown in Fig. 13. In this image, over-resolved vortical flow is coloured in red, while under-resolved flow regions are marked blue. White indicates the chosen threshold of 80 % resolved turbulent kinetic energy.

All near wall regions, especially near the lip of the nozzle extensions, show strongly under-resolved vortical (stream-wise) structures. This effect is known as the grey-area problem in Detached-Eddy simulations and refers to spatial areas where a delayed transition from modelled turbulent kinetic to resolved vortices happens. Near flow separation, the modelled turbulent kinetic energy is reduced while (resolved) vortices are being formed. Due to the nature of the simulation, both processes don't happen instantaneously and require a small but of time or length to develop. This effect is referred to as the grey-area problem and is sometimes solved by introducing synthetic turbulent fluctuations to speed up the process. Another method [7], also used in TAU, is to orient the subgrid-scale filter definition to the formation of large vortical structures. This helps to accelerate the formation of resolved turbulent structures compared to classical (isotropic) subgrid-scale models.

3.6. Sensitivity of the $Ma = 0.9$ Results Towards Mesh Refinement

Even though mesh convergence cannot generally be expected for scale-resolving simulations, the sensitivity of the unsteady pressure loads towards mesh refinement shall be investigated in more detail in this section. Therefore, a refined mesh for the $Ma = 0.9$ case consisting of 36.72 mio points has been created. It is based on the previous (baseline) $Ma = 0.9$ mesh but significantly refined in the base region of the T3 vehicle.

Fig. 14. Comparison of the vortical structures around the T3 vehicle using the Q -criterion for two different mesh resolutions. A non-dimensional value of 50 was chosen for Q' .

As expected, the finer mesh results in more resolved vortical structures for a given nondimensional Q' value of 50 (see Fig. 14). The overall structure of the flow field remains the same indicating that most of the vortices are being shed by the lateral nozzle extensions and the rocket base edge.

Fig. 15. Normalized surface RMS pressure distribution on the baseplate for the $Ma = 0.9$ case. Comparison between the baseline and the refined mesh.

To compare the surface pressure levels more quantitatively, the RMS pressure values are shown in Fig. 15 for the baseline and the fine mesh. For brevity, only the baseplate picture are shown. The unsteady pressure load distribution is very similar to the coarser baseline mesh, with the highest value near the base plate edge on the leeward side. This corresponds to the previously shown Q -isosurface images that show a strong impingement of vortices in these areas. If at all,

only minor differences in the surface RMS pressure values can be observed.

Table 3 gives a summary the maximum value of the surface RMS pressure on different surface parts of the T3 vehicle. In general, the grid refinement seems to decrease the maximum unsteady pressure loads by about 1-2 %. However, both simulations predict the maximum value on the whole vehicle on the outer nozzle walls with 42.2 % for the baseline mesh and 40.5 % for the fine mesh.

Table 3. Summary of maximum surface RMS values for the baseline and refined mesh.

Part	Maximum RMS baseline mesh	Maximum RMS fine mesh
Baseplate	41.1 %	39.8 %
Nozzle	42.2 %	40.5 %
Body	20.0 %	19.2 %

It can be concluded from this study that the mesh resolution only has a minor influence on the shape and maximum value of the surface RMS pressure value distribution, therefore showing the robustness of our numerical approach.

4. CONCLUSION

This work investigated unsteady surface pressure loads for the T3 future reference configuration for a reusable launcher demonstrator at two different trajectory points in an unpropelled gliding phase. The goal of this work was to give an overview of the spatial unsteady pressure distribution on the vehicle surface, to identify the regions of highest activity and to quantify the amplitude of the pressure loads as a percentage of the freestream dynamic pressure. Our work shows that for the given angle of attack, most vortices are being shed from the edge of the lateral nozzle extensions and impinge on the launcher base edge where the highest unsteady loads are found. Additionally, a recirculation zone forms between the nozzle exit plane and the base plate which causes high unsteady loads on the nozzle outer walls. The highest pressure RMS values are found there for the $Ma = 0.9$ configuration at 42.2 % of the dynamic freestream pressure. For the supersonic $Ma = 1.5$ case, the maximum unsteady pressure levels were about 10 % lower.

This work also investigated single-point pressure spectra at selected positions on the nozzle surface (inside and outside). We found rather broadband spectra of turbulent fluctuations with distinct peaks only in the low frequency band up to $Sr = 0.2$ and around $Sr = 0.8$. At the chosen locations, the supersonic test case showed higher low-frequency peaks than the subsonic flight state. A further analysis of the turbulent time-scale revealed that the total simulation length of approximately one second is presumably too small to obtain well

converged single-point spectral plots. This problem, however, can be alleviated by increasing the total simulation time.

The last part of this paper is concerned with an analysis of the grid resolution of this scale-resolving iDDDES. By invoking the so-called grid sensor, we showed that more than 80 % of the turbulent kinetic energy is resolved in the region of interest. This is one indication supporting the validity of our numerical approach. Additionally, we also investigated the sensitivity of the surface RMS pressure towards mesh refinement and we found that the overall shape and maximum RMS value only changed by about 1.7 %. This is another indication that the chosen modelling approach is robust towards variations in the grid resolution.

5. REFERENCES

- [1] D. Schwamborn, T. Gerhold, and R. Heinrich, "The DLR-TAU-Code: Recent applications in research and industry," in *Proceedings of the European Conference on Computational Fluid Dynamics (ECOMAS)*, 2006.
- [2] A Probst, J. Löwe, S. Reuß, T. Knopp, and R. Kessler, "Scale-resolving simulations with a low-dissipation low-dispersion second-order scheme for unstructured finite-volume flow solvers," in *53rd AIAA Aerospace Sciences Meeting*, 2015.
- [3] Mikhail L Shur, Philippe R Spalart, Mikhail Kh Strelets, and Andrey K Travin, "A hybrid RANS-LES approach with delayed-DES and wall-modelled LES capabilities," *International Journal of Heat and Fluid Flow*, vol. 29, no. 6, pp. 1638–1649, 2008.
- [4] Jan-Erik Schumann, Volker Hannemann, and Klaus Hannemann, "Investigation of structured and unstructured grid topology and resolution dependence for scale-resolving simulations of axisymmetric detaching-reattaching shear layers," in *Progress in Hybrid RANS-LES Modelling*, Yannick Hoarau et al., Ed., November 2019, vol. 143.
- [5] Gal Berkooz, Philip Holmes, and John L Lumley, "The proper orthogonal decomposition in the analysis of turbulent flows," *Annual review of fluid mechanics*, vol. 25, no. 1, pp. 539–575, 1993.
- [6] Silvia Reuß, T Knopp, A Probst, and M Orlt, "Assessment of local LES-resolution sensors for hybrid RANS/LES simulations," in *Progress in Hybrid RANS-LES Modelling*, pp. 93–103. Springer, 2015.
- [7] Silvia Reuß, *A Grid-Adaptive Algebraic Hybrid RANS/LES Method*, Dissertation, Georg-August Universität Göttingen, 2015.

Acknowledgements

Funded by the European Union under the grant agreement ID 101082007. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or European Health and Digital Executive Agency. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.